

STUDIES IN SULPHONES. PART III* SYNTHESIS OF NEW CONTACT INSECTICIDES†

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Syntheses of *p*-chlorophenylchloromethylsulphone, the active principle of the German insecticide "Leuseto neu" and five of its analogues have been described.

Busvine (*Nature*, 1946, 158, 22) has shown that the active principle of the new type of German insecticide "Leuseto neu" used during the World War II, is *p*-chlorophenylchloromethylsulphone.

Although it is more toxic to lice and bed-bugs than D. D. T., it suffers from the disadvantage that its solubility in mineral oil is low. No details of the synthesis of this compound are yet available. Since this opens up fresh field for research on synthetic insecticides, it was thought of interest to synthesise this and a few analogous compounds.

By reacting the sodium salt of *p*-acetaminobenzene sulphinic acid ("Organic Synthesis", Coll. vol. I, p.8) with dichloroacetic acid, *p*-acetaminophenylchloromethylsulphone (I) is obtained. This on hydrolysis with hydrochloric acid gives *p*-aminophenylchloromethylsulphone (II).

Compound (II) on diazotisation and further subjecting to Sandmeyer's reaction yields *p*-chlorophenyl- (III), *p*-bromophenyl- (IV), and *p*-iodophenyl- (V) chloromethylsulphones Sandmeyer's reaction using cuprous cyanide for the synthesis of *p*-CN-substituted analogue does not take place in a facile manner. On heating the diazonium solution of (II), *p*-hydroxyphenylchloromethylsulphone (VI) is obtained.

Dichloroacetic acid reacts with *p*-chlorobenzene sulphinic acid in alkaline solution to form the unstable chlorophenylchlorocarboxymethylsulphone (not isolated) which furnishes *p*-chlorophenylchloromethylsulphone (III) by the elimination of one molecule of carbon dioxide.

It is interesting to record that the insecticidal action of *p*-chlorophenylchloromethylsulphone in the case of the very common weevil (*Calandra oryzae*) affecting rice, wheat and jowar in storage, has been found to be very unsatisfactory, the average percentage mortality after 72 hours of exposure being not more than 37, even at 100% concentration, the material having been intimately mixed

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† The two previous parts in the series are :

Part I : *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 24, 194. (cf. *Science & Culture*, 1945, 11, 567).

Part II : A note on the Preparation of Promin (*Science & Culture*, 1945, 11, 568).

with jowar at the rate of 1 oz. for every 100 pounds. This finding raises the question if *p*-chlorophenylchloromethylsulphone is highly selective in its insecticidal action or if it is really the active constituent of *Leuseto neu*. The problem requires further scrutiny.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

p-Acetaminophenylchloromethylsulphone (I).—*p*-Acetaminobenzene sulphinic acid (20 g.) and dichloroacetic acid (13 g.) were dissolved in water (100 c. c.) containing sodium hydroxide (8.5 g.) and heated under reflux. After 2 hours a precipitate separated out. This was filtered on cooling and the filtrate was again refluxed for another 6 hours when a further quantity of precipitate was thrown out. This was collected and combined with the first lot, washed with water and crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 204-205°, yield 16 g. The product gave no effervescence with sodium bicarbonate indicating that decarboxylation also had occurred.

The same product was obtained even when the reaction was carried out with two molecular proportion of *p*-acetaminobenzene sulphinic acid to one of dichloroacetic acid. (Found : N, 5.6. $C_9H_{10}O_5NClS$ requires N, 5.65 per cent).

p-Aminophenylchloromethylsulphone (II).—Compound (I, 12 g.) was refluxed with 5*N*-HCl (120 c. c.) for 2 hours. The resulting solution, on cooling, was neutralised with ammonia when a colourless crystalline precipitate was obtained. This was collected, washed with water and crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 98°, yield 9.5 g. (Found : N, 6.75. $C_7H_8O_2NClS$ requires N, 6.8 per cent).

p-Chlorophenylchloromethylsulphone (III).—(a). Compound (II, 5 g.) dissolved in 5*N*-HCl (25 c. c.) was diazotised in the usual manner with sodium nitrite (2 g.) dissolved in water (10 c. c.). Cuprous chloride solution (30 c. c., 10%) was then added to the diazonium solution and it was refluxed until evolution of nitrogen ceased. It was then cooled and the precipitate separating was collected, washed with water and crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 120°, yield 4 g. (Found : S, 14.2. $C_7H_6O_2Cl_2S$ requires S, 14.3 per cent).

(b). *p*-Chlorobenzene sulphinic acid (8.9 g.), prepared according to Gattermann (*Ber.*, 1899, 32, 1142; 1908, 41, 3320) and dichloroacetic acid (6.5 g.) were dissolved in water (50 c. c.) containing sodium hydroxide (4.5 g.) and boiled under reflux for 8 hours when a crystalline precipitate separated. This was collected, washed with water and crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 120°, yield 6 g. It did not give effervescence with sodium bicarbonate. Carbon dioxide was evolved from the alkaline mother-liquor on acidification. The same compound resulted when the reaction was conducted with two molecular proportion of *p*-chlorobenzene sulphinic acid. There was no depression in melting point on admixture with the product prepared as detailed in (a).

p-Bromophenylchloromethylsulphone (IV).—A solution of cuprous bromide, prepared from copper sulphate (4.15 g.), potassium bromide (12 g.), water (25 c.c.), conc. sulphuric acid (4 g.) and copper turnings (6 g.) was added to the diazonium solution obtained from compound (II, 5 g.) as detailed under (a) above, and boiled under reflux until evolution of nitrogen ceased and the product worked out in the usual manner. m.p. 145-46°, yield 4.4 g. (Found : S, 11.61. $C_7H_6O_2ClBrS$ requires S, 11.87 per cent).

p-Iodophenylchloromethylsulphone (V).—A solution of potassium iodide (10 g.) in water (15 c.c.) was added to the diazonium solution obtained from compound (II, 5 g.) and the product worked out as in (IV), m.p. 172°, yield 5 g. (Found : S, 10.12. $C_7H_6O_2ClIS$ requires S, 10.10 per cent).

p-Hydroxyphenylchloromethylsulphone (VI).—The diazonium solution from compound (II, 10 g.) on being heated on a water-bath for 2 hours gave the product which was crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 144°, yield 8.2 g. (Found : S, 15.32. $C_7H_7O_3ClS$ requires S, 15.5 per cent).

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